

Human ethos of Paulo Coelho's selected novels: A Critico-Thematic analysis

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ABSTRACT

The study analyzes the patterns or themes of the five (5) novels of Paulo Coelho, namely: *The Alchemist*, *Brida*, *By the River Piedra I Sat Down and Wept*, *Eleven Minutes*, and *The Zahir*. The study is primarily anchored on the 20th century Literary Humanism and supported by Expressivism. By these, the researchers utilize the critico-thematic analysis to determine the themes of the selected novels. The study also seeks the themes of human life as depicted in the selected novels and how these themes are enhanced by the use of Coelho's personal writing techniques. The study finds out that these novels portray not only the literal journey of the characters but also reflects the journey towards self-actualization through spiritual enlightenment and dream-realization. Thus, the study concludes that a man can fulfill his or her destiny when he or she has contributed something to the world that can affect change.

Keywords: *critico-thematic analysis, expressivism, human ethos, Paulo Coelho's representative novels, literary humanism*

I. INTRODUCTION

Art is a conscious use of skill and creative imagination especially in the production of aesthetic objects or works. According to literary critic Shōyō (2013), it is something that gives man pleasure and improves his disposition. Literature, on the other hand, is a written art which expresses the significant human experience in well-chosen and arranged words. Therefore, when art and text blend, literature is born and from that literary acumen man's philosophical, moral, and spiritual qualities are developed. Fenollosa (1908) as cited by Shōyō (1981) believed that art ultimately enhances life by the pleasure it produces. Thus,

as a consequence, it construes delight and instruction that ultimately creates the experience of literature-and from that experience transpires the virtue of learning leading to a discerning reader's multi-dimensional development.

A novel, as a literary form of art, is a fictional piece of prose that is typically written in a narrative style and presented in a book form. With its voluminous form, it attempts to accurately imitate human nature as well as social conditions by realistically representing the mysteries embedded in man's life in the society and the milieu that he lives. Its fundamental importance,

as far as its contribution to the philosophical, moral, aesthetic, and spiritual development of an individual, is by means of the experience that it offers.

A novel provides a visceral experience in the sense that it facilitates development or enhancement of an individual's creative power in order to shape his or her own reality through the pleasure that he or she experiences when he or she imagines future events. This personal experience would spark the reader's interest, if not, conversely, a particular personal encounter that the reader would seek in the novel in order to augment his or her present situation through the characters' depiction of their roles. Furthermore, a novel offers an emotional experience that extends the reader's emotional repertoire and self-understanding, for a novel conveys an idea and enfolds such in a comprehensible perspective that a perceptive individual can visualize how that idea or situation may unfold in the real world. By focusing one's reading on a particular theme, the reader gathers a collection of reference experiences that are connected to a particular subject that would be relevant to his or her present or future circumstances (Bollenbach, 2008).

The current reception of man towards reading a novel has greatly transformed. A study conducted by the Social Weather Stations (SWS) as commissioned by the National Book Development Board in 2012 reveals, in particular, the attitude of the Filipinos towards reading. Sadly, it shows that people primarily read in order to impetuously gain knowledge and information, thereby reclosing the notion of reading to delight in order to learn, which is one of the basic tenets of literature and apparently, one of the bare essentials of human life, as every human being is from time to time subjected to the dilemma of searching for truth while at the same time is trapped between what he is and what he ought to be.

Thus, the study also links with the necessity to promote the love for reading to Filipinos not only to address their desire for information, but also to cultivate the more profound side of pleasure by introducing the value of arts and literature into their very lives. After all, it can be inferred from the survey that it is not only religious satisfaction per se that man seeks while reading especially the

Bible as he or she is in constant quest for his or her self and for his or her utmost purpose. It is with this quest of man that arts and literature can equip him or her with knowledge, since literary texts, especially the novel, teaches lessons by tapping the emotion, senses, and imagination of the reader. In this respect, it serves as a guide book to life in passing on much needed information to one's self.

Thus accordingly, the study aspires to ultimately analyze the patterns and themes, and delve into developing the reader's attitude specifically that of the students, toward learning through pleasure using a novel as a vessel of instruction, particularly that of the selected works of the international best-selling writer, Paulo Coelho. In addition, it also looks into educating them to the deeper gamut of the significance of the novel in elucidating life and the myriads of ways in which individuals can learn in a delightful manner by means of stirring up their curiosity and igniting their thirst for adventure, fun, and creativity while simultaneously injecting moral lessons through the themes presented in novels to strengthen their learning aptitude.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The study is primarily anchored on the 20th century Literary Humanism which centers almost exclusively on literary culture. Petrarch (1374), Father of Literary Humanism, believed that it is the accumulated wisdom from literature and letters that fosters the individual in alleviating his life. In his 1362 letter to his friend Boccaccio, Petrarch, as cited by Sadlon (2007), intensely emphasized his belief on the positive role of literature to the individual, in that for a good mind, literature stimulates the love of virtue and it weakens the trepidation of death. Moreover, he also regarded that literature does not hinder one's development, but rather it helps the properly constituted mind. Thus, it facilitates a person's life (Petrarca, Robinson & Rolfe, 1898). To exclusively define the scope of Literary Humanism, the 20th century Literary Humanists confined the discipline's tenets specifically within the range of literary culture that primarily accentuates the idea that literature can help an individual to achieve personal understanding and development

through introspection and retrospection. For these scholars, literature can lead the readers to postulate a unique individual experience by providing the reader with an opportunity to examine his own conscious thoughts and feelings. On the other hand, literary text also bestows the reader the opportunity to look back and examine the past events that may assist him in understanding his present situation.

Apart from the 20th century Literary Humanism, this study is also supported by Expressivism which deems that a literary work has the capacity to elicit feelings from its readers. It focuses on the study of the author's feelings, thus believing that the author of a literary piece does not mimic the outside world, but conveys his internal world. Because of this, it rests on the notion that by reading how another individual feels, one's own sensibilities are also awakened, thereby developing one's personality. In the study, Literary Humanism theory insisted that the best, and indeed the only way to study literature was to study the text itself in close detail, and to disregard anything outside the text itself, including the author's biography, the historical context in which the work appeared, how it related to other works both before, during, and after its appearance, and how critics and readers responded to the text. In short, this branch of criticism theorized the literary text as an isolated object, something to be studied in and of itself alone. This is the theory that says what literature students ought to do is read the words on the page, and nothing else. Conversely, Expressivism is used to determine the writer's inner psychology. Whatever the writer writes expresses the subconscious or unconscious workings of his minds which are products of his or her own personal experiences in life. More so, the patterns and/or themes found in the selected novels of Paulo Coelho determine the author's personal experiences in life.

Hence, in the present epoch that man is living in, he is continually subdued not only with questions pertaining to himself, but also with limitations placed upon by society, laws, mores, customs, traditions, family, and even self-perception that make him surrender to the great possibilities ahead of him or her. Paulo Coelho, an author of the international best-selling novels,

believes that one can be a master of the things that try to enslave him by taking responsibility. Thus, it is deemed that the only crime against life is to believe in the word "impossible". The moment an individual succumbs to repose on that word, he has already failed.

Furthermore, he also believes that each individual has a unique role to play, whether he is a writer or a reader. For Paulo Coelho, it is not the book by itself that changes a person's life; nevertheless, change on the person can occur through the sensations purported by the writer that may have an effect on the reader. When the writer writes about a topic, a philosophy, or an idea at the right moment when the reader is desperately struggling to find answers to his questions or simply to emancipate him from his present dilemma, he creates a bridge. It makes the reader feel that he is not alone. But someone also feels the same way that he does. With that, a connection between the writer and the reader is developed. The reader feels that the author is writing about him, so then he is persuaded to do what the characters in the novel have done or to follow what the author has written in the book. By doing so, a reader is then transformed to a level where he is inspired to take a risk towards the fulfillment of his destiny. As the novel encourages one to escape from the humdrum of daily life and allows one to submerge himself in the pages of the book, so does it also help one to remember to be hopeful, to take practical support, and to grasp a few life lessons from it (Roberts & Crawford, 2008).

Paulo Coelho, an author of international best-selling novels, is known not only for the multi-dimensional scope of his works, encompassing the disciplines of History, Geography, Mythology, Philosophy, Theology, and Psychology, but also on his themes addressing the issues that man collectively want to address but is afraid to verbalize, such as man's individual power, the view of sex and marriage, and love in its multifaceted form, which are further enhanced by his skillful application of moral parables expressing a conception of right conduct, of the established ceremony surrounding any form of ritual, of simple narration of useful truth in fables, of extraordinary event or religious miracles, of

awkward questions which are normally regarded by the social norms and mores as taboo, and of time frame that is regarded as a period of time when certain things are expected to happen. With his atypical and unconventional philosophy, Coelho took the courage to play on with his contradictory nature and learned to turn them around to his advantage, resulting to a gross of 145 million books sold and translated into 74 languages in total, to date. Calio (1970) made an analytical study on the pessimistic themes of Thomas Hardy's selected Victorian novels to bring to the attention of the readers the significance of pessimism as portrayed by the author in the major characters and events using analytical and descriptive methods. The themes he found from the novels include the themes of love and marriage, hopes and intentions, sex and marriage, but with the characters showing increasing gravity of pessimism. Narca (1997) additionally studied on the themes of love, beauty, death, and life in the selected short stories and poems of Edgar Allan Poe enhanced by the techniques of imagery and symbolism employing critico-analysis method.

Cobita (2003) undertook an analysis of the themes and literary techniques in the selected works of Robert Penn Warren, utilizing the critico-analytical method of research. As such, she was able to draw out the themes of good versus evil, Machiavellian expediency, spiritual odyssey, tragic flow, and the search for a father enhanced with Warren's techniques of flashback, point of view, symbolism, and analogy. Moreover, Muraleedharan (2013), in his Multi-Disciplinary Dimensions in Paulo Coelho's Novel *The Alchemist*, analyzed how Coelho portrayed the self-realization theme of the alchemist using the different disciplines of History, Geography, Philosophy, Theology, Psychology, and Mythology, as contained in the novel.

Dash (2013) in his *Alchemy of the Soul: A Comparative Study of Hermann Hesse's Siddharta and Paulo Coelho's The Alchemist* investigated not only the differences and similarities of the two modern classic novels, but also how each can be interpreted using Jung's psychoanalytic process of Individuation or Self-realization.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study utilized the critico-thematic

analysis approach. This method emphasizes identifying, examining, and recording patterns or themes within the data. A theme represents a level of patterned meaning from the data that is connected to the research questions at hand. In choosing the data, a purposive technique of data selection was used. Out of 30 books, to date, written by Paulo Coelho, the researchers opted to focus on five of his works, namely: *The Alchemist* (1988), *Brida* (1990), *By the River Piedra I Sat Down and Wept* (1994), *Eleven Minutes* (2003), and *The Zahir* (2005), first and foremost on the basis of their intimate connection to the aspects where man is constantly subjected to, such as self-realization, in subjects concerning love, sex, and marriage, fate and will, concept about life, and religion and spirituality. The above novels were also selected by virtue of their connection to the human life, depicting common issues faced by man, for instance self-realization, love, vision of life, religion and spirituality, fate and will, sex, and marriage.

In order to accomplish the desired result, the researchers utilized the critico-thematic analysis approach. Thus, in order to acquire accurate findings on her study, the following steps were undertaken: Phase 1: Reading and re-reading of the data, that is, of the novels for the researchers to become familiar with the themes and techniques used in writing them; Phase 2: Creation of the initial codes by documenting where and how patterns occur, that is, if there is any in the course of reading. For the purpose of the study, a code refers to the label that is given to particular pieces of the data that contribute to a theme; Phase 3: Combination of codes to form clustered themes in order to accurately depict the data; Phase 4: Inspection of the researchers at how the themes support the data; Phase 5: Synthesis of same themes to produce a comprehensive analysis; and Phase 6: Composition of the analysis report.

Following this, examination of each datum is to be undertaken by reading each novel and taking down the relevant information needed in the study, such as the illustrated themes in the novels. Finally, with the collected variables, the researchers would then synthesize and analyze how these different themes of human life are enhanced by moral parables, fable, ritual, religious

miracles, awkward questions, and time frame in the selected novels.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Paulo Coelho's novels are known for compelling the fundamental themes that speak of the basic human nature, as well as the basic communal questions that humans are often asking: about self, dreams, love, religion and spirituality, self-realization, and the vision of life. Even though the themes of his novels differ from one story to another, definite patterns can be found throughout his works (Coelho, 2009).

The theme is the central or dominating idea of a story; in that, it is the total meaning in the work after having wholly taken into account the entire literary piece's aspect, and accordingly may be demonstrated by the characters' actions, utterances, or thoughts. Consequently, this part undertakes the critico-analysis of the common themes in the novels of Paulo Coelho, namely: *The Alchemist*; *Brida*; *By the River Piedra I Sat Down and Wept*; *Eleven Minutes*; and *The Zahir*.

Journey. There are two types of journey themes identified in the representative novels of Paulo Coelho: The first is the transformational journey towards self-realization. Narca (1997) maintained that this type of journey signifies the change of emotions, intellect undergoing a travel to other situations of one's life, behavior, and personality; that every step along the way has significance relative to the culmination of the individual's reason for self-actualization.

For a person to be a fully functioning individual, Rogers (1961) deemed the actuality of the congruence between self—that is the sense of who the person is, and the ideal self—who that person feels he should be. Other than that, Abrams & Harpham (2012) recognized peak experiences. This means that the moments in one's life that take one beyond his ordinary perceptions, thoughts, and feelings, causing the individual to feel energized, or more alive, thus transforming his understanding of his self and the world.

Jung (1933) described it as the "alchemy of the soul", which is more commonly known as Individuation or Self-Realization. He dedicated approximately twenty years to the analysis of alchemy, leading him to the discovery that the

alchemical testing of transmuting base metal or lead into gold reflected an internal developmental process of wholeness and health in the human psyche (Dash, 2013).

In order to attain self-realization, a person has to manifest the contents of his unconscious state into the conscious state, for the unconscious and the conscious are opposites; however, they are at the same time complementary. The unconscious is divided into two: the personal and the collective unconscious. The collective unconscious is composed of archetypes, autonomous instincts, patterns, or behaviors which encompass time, places, and people. Since the unconscious state exercises great power, and by gaining the upper hand, collective unconscious can perform miracles—one of which is self-realization.

The transformational journey is illustrated in the characters of Santiago and the Englishman in *The Alchemist*, Brida and the Magus in *Brida*, Pilar and her boyfriend in *By the River Piedra I Sat Down and Wept*, Maria and Ralf Hart in *Eleven Minutes*, and the narrator and Esther in *The Zahir*.

In *The Alchemist*, Santiago started his journey in order to find out the truth of his recurrent dream of buried treasure in the Pyramids of Egypt, which is called by the old wise king named Melchizedek as his Personal Legend. It is what one has always wanted to accomplish of which he ultimately realized. However, on the course of his journey towards the Pyramids, his being has been transformed as well: he started to believe in personal omens or signs, learned the universal language of the world sometimes known as "intuition" or "hunch" and applied it in his day to day life; decided to trust himself as well as the others, understood his heart including its fear and desires; recognized that everything is interconnected and is part of him, and he needed both the animate and inanimate if he is to understand his self and the world; and most importantly he learned that he is the replica of God, that is, God's spirit dwells in him that allows him to perform miracles. Thus, the acme of his spiritual journey of self-actualization is finding his mission on earth that of being able to perform miracles because of the realization that God's Spirit dwells in him.

The Englishman, on the other hand, dreams of

ultimately becoming an alchemist. He started his journey by studying for ten years in the university in order to learn about Esperanto, an artificial language invented as a means of international communication; the world's religion, and all other subjects that would help him find the one true language of the universe; and went on to a caravan bound for Al-Fayoum oasis where the real alchemist lives to seek for his help. In realizing his dream, he came to realize that he must not fear failure for this apprehension was the very reason of his previous setback in achieving the Master Work, that is, the Philosopher's Stone. As a result, he continues on doing and trying to do what the alchemist has instructed him.

In the novel *Brida*, the protagonist named Brida desires to become a witch, so she sought the aid of the Magus who taught her the teachings of the Tradition of the Sun and of the wisdom about things, and Wicca who educated her of the Tradition of the Moon, that includes, to perform the different rituals corresponding to the different cycles of the moon; to dance in tune to the Sound of the World, to identify the different cures of herbs, and to feel the energy or vibes of the clothes she owns. Her journey is more of a spiritual transformation. Through the rituals and exercises that Wicca assigned her to do, she was able to awaken the dormant voice of her soul that signified her readiness to be initiated as a full-pledged witch. However, her journey did not stop there. The ultimate condition for her self-actualization is her aptitude to transform all the knowledge she has learned into wisdom through the use of the force of sex as it opens the portal to both real and magical worlds. With the help of her soul mates, she was able to attain the pinnacle of her journey in both the spiritual and material planes.

The Magus, conversely, is a man who isolated himself from the world, an act he dutifully performs as a recompense for his prior violation on the law of love. He was in love and got hurt, but the worst part of it was that he violated the fundamental law of love: interfering in one's free will. His only redemption is to wait for his soul mate to arrive and set him free from his bondage without his interference or manipulation of any kind to encourage the growth of love. His journey

started in his detachment from the world as his penalty and spent most of his life in the forest learning from it. However, the forest presented him another lesson that would define his existence in the form of Brida—his soul mate. His journey with Brida taught him patience, and most importantly, to love freely without expecting anything in return. To be a fully actualized person, the Magus had eventually learned that love is liberty, and because of that discernment, he is again free to return to the world and has continued on being a Teacher of the Tradition of the Sun.

Pilar of the novel *By the River Piedra I Sat Down and Wept* began her journey of transformation the moment when she heard her seminarian friend's message on his conference in Madrid about taking risks and identifying magic moments. From an individual who was always defined by plans for everyday survival, her journey from Madrid to Saint-Savin in France where the grotto of Lourdes is situated, she was transformed into a person who learns to follow her heart instead. Because of that, she was able to re-discover her being and discerned her mission of spreading the Great Mothers' love side by side with her boyfriend. On the other hand, it is also an odyssey of love that commenced during childhood, of love that was lost, and was recovered in her adult life despite of the vehement tests of prejudices, distinctive views and religious orientations, and altered dreams. With her re-discovered faith, she was able to recover her lost love in the form of her seminarian friend, and together, they eventually set to trudge their selected path.

Her boyfriend, on the other hand, underwent spiritual pilgrimage by heeding the spiritual call of religious order in order to meet God and ultimately discerned his gift-his would-be way of serving the world. From a teenager who was merely interested to gain knowledge outside his small town of Soria, he reached the monastery in France to seek God and to renounce his budding love for Pilar. His insatiable search for spiritual satisfaction brought him to India; however, it was in his stay in the monastery in Pyrenees that he met with God and developed his gift of performing miracles. Nevertheless, he still had to resolve his inner turmoil in order to realize his true being: to leave the seminary and be with Pilar, or to

renounce his love for Pilar and continue with his mission of healing. To settle this dilemma, he spent some time with Pilar and realized that he still loved her, prompting him to surrender his mission. But this decision saddened Pilar. With her help and forgiveness, he was able to start dreaming again and moved forward to the attainment of his dream.

In *Eleven Minutes*, Maria dreamed of true love. In her teenage years, she learned about love and heartaches, and discovered the other not-so-good side of sex, which actually was the commencement of her journey to finding true love. After high school she worked as a sales girl in a fabric shop in her small town, and with enough savings, she went to Rio de Janeiro for a week-long vacation. As chance presented itself, she grabbed the opportunity of going to Geneva to work as a cabaret dancer; however, this did not last long. She resigned and applied for a modeling job which led to an encounter with an Arab gentleman who paid her one thousand francs in exchange of the sexual pleasure she could give. Because of despair, and the desire not to go home empty-handed, she succumbed to prostitution. From her profession, she learned a myriad of things like playing the role of different persona in different occasions such as, being a courtesan, a mother, a listener, and a friend to satisfy her customers' needs. When the time was right, fate had presented her true love in the form of Ralf Hart, with whom she re-discovered her lost self that was long-buried in heaps of pains, failures, and activities she had engaged with.

Conversely, Ralf Hart was divorced twice, and although he possessed good looks, success, and wealth, he still has problem with sex and love. He went to the Copacabana Bar in order to seek solace to his problem, but usually got despaired. Then one day, when his soul was ready, he met Maria, whom he referred to as having a special light. Intrigued, he made an appointment with her in the bar as her customer. During their sessions, she taught him about gift-giving, to acknowledge the other person's existence; of radiating desire without having to give the object of desire; and about exploring of each other's body without sexual contact. In their respective separate ways, they were molded to the maximum in order to prepare each of them to the realization of their

individual dreams and in realizing their true selves in return.

The narrator of *The Zahir* embarked more on a spiritual journey in order to recover his wife; thus, in turn resulted to his personal transformation. He was a successful writer, a celebrity in fact, and possessed the same weakness of a typical married man: forgetful to demonstrate his love to his wife assuming that she had already known about it. His pilgrimage has subtly dawned on the day when Esther, his wife had disappeared. However, anger, pain, pride, and the need to move on clouded his desire to find her. Then one day, in the book signing event, he met for the first time Mikhail, the person he suspected as his wife's lover. Mikhail unconsciously rekindled in him the desire to find his wife; and eventually, the realization of his shortcomings; the acceptance of his own imperfections; and the resolve to be a better person in order to be deserving of Esther's love again. From Paris, his journey to find Esther, continued to Vitoria in Spain where he wrote his best-selling book about his love for his wife; to the Armenian restaurant where Mikhail performed every Thursday night, where he learned about the instances displaying the lack of love; to the subsequent meetings with Mikhail who introduced him to the streets of Paris where he met the beggars who became part of Esther's life and to the group whose motto is to live today as if it is the last, and as if it is the first; to Croatia, where he made a pact with God that if he could perform a particular act, he would take it as a sign to go to Central Asia to find his wife; and to the Kazakhstan steppes where he was blessed and was taught the tradition of the steppes. His spiritual journey was best reflected in his conversation with Mikhail:

...but that didn't just make me travel across the Kazakhstan steppes: it made me travel through the whole of my past life. I saw where I went wrong, I saw where I stopped, I saw the moment where I lost Esther, the moment of the giving-up point. I experienced things I never imagined I would experience at my age...

On the other hand, Esther's despondency on love—primarily on the reason that she could no longer generate love for the lack of reciprocal love from her husband, and the desire to live life to the fullest, had ventured into the warring zones of Africa, then to Central Asia to find meaning in her life. In one of her visits to Central Asia, she met Mikhail who became her friend, and who helped her generate love. She also learned about Tangri, the tradition of the steppes, which speaks of opening the channel of her soul in order to replenish and renew the imprisoned energy of love, which is the basic reason for one's unhappiness. Apart from that, she also came in contact with the beggars and with various people in order to put into practice the teachings of the tradition. Finally, she stayed in a Kazakh village to fully understand life and waited for her husband to come to her at the right time.

Nevertheless, the novels speak of the literal journey, as an act of travelling from one place to another. In *The Alchemist*, Santiago traversed many lands and two continents in quest of his treasure. From his native Andalusia, he crossed the Strait of Gibraltar and reached the African continent through the Port of Tangier. From there, he crossed the vast desert and reached Al-Fayoum oasis, and finally arrived in Egypt where his supposed-treasures are buried, only to learn later that he has to return to his native Andalusia particularly in the old abandoned church where he usually sleeps with his flock.

Pilar, on one hand, lived in a small Spanish town named Soria. She moved to a bigger city named Zaragoza to continue with her higher education. After so many years, she embarked on her journey to the capital Madrid to see her childhood friend. With changed perception and attitude towards life, she went with him to Bilbao, then to Navarra, afterwards to San Martin de Unx, where they both crossed the Pyrenees mountain chain bordering Spain and France to reach Saint-Savin in order to attend the feast of the Immaculate Conception in Lourdes. After the Feast, they had a return trip to Saint-Savin, then to San Martin de Unx, before they reached Piedra, a town in Spain where they visited when they were still young.

Maria's journey, on the other hand, is composed of her small and remote village in Brazil

as the starting point. When she was then nineteen years old, she travelled, for the first time, outside her hometown to the Brazilian financial capital Rio de Janeiro. With much luck, she met a Swiss man who brought her to Geneva, Switzerland, where she stayed for more than a year. Her journey stopped in Paris.

Finally, the narrator of *The Zahir* has been to many places, starting from his own country. He went to Spain to undertake a pilgrimage to the road of Santiago de Compostela. After that pilgrimage, he decided to settle for a while in Madrid then went back to his own country again. However, because of his writing career, he opted to live in Paris. Due to the nature of his work, he would go to other parts of Spain, like Madrid, Vitoria, and Bayonne. He would also go to the United States of America, Geneva in Switzerland, Amsterdam, Zagreb in Croatia, and Milan in Italy to visit his new girlfriend. Nonetheless, since he was still obsessed with his wife, he reached Central Asia, particularly in Kazakhstan to find her.

Love. The theme of love in its varied facets is portrayed in the selected novels of Paulo Coelho. The theme of unconditional love is tackled in *The Alchemist*. It can be summarized in the utterance of the alchemist to Santiago one night when the latter was skeptical to continue in pursuing his journey towards the Pyramids and to leave Fatima behind in the oasis: "You must understand that love never keeps a man from pursuing his Personal Legend. If he abandons that pursuit, it's because it wasn't true love... the love that speaks the Language of the World."

Relatively, *Brida* also undertakes the theme of unconditional love, which can be reflected in the statement of the Magus concerning her love for Brida after the latter's initiation rites:

"When we first met—although it seems to me that I've always known you, because I can't remember the world before that... I knew you were my Soul Mate, and that you would teach me everything I needed to learn... Then you came and I understood all of this. You came to free me from the slavery I myself had created, to tell me that I was free to return to the world and to

the things of the world... I will always remember now that love is liberty...."

On the other hand, it is also reflected in Pilar's silent prayer to the Great Mother in *By the River Piedra I Sat Down and Wept*:

"...Give me the opportunity to learn through my love, because love has never kept anyone away from their dreams...";

as well as *Eleven Minutes* as contained in Maria's diary page where she admitted her love for Ralf Hart:

"... I allowed myself to fall in love for one simple reason: I'm not expecting anything to come of it..."; and

The *Zahir*, specifically on Esther's love for her husband, as reflected on by him while writing his first book:

"... the woman who made me say yes when I wanted to say no, who forced me to fight for what she, quite rightly, believed was my reason for living, who let me set off alone because her love for me was greater even than her love for herself, who made me go in search of my dream."

Philistia or self-love is illustrated in the novel *The Zahir*. As elucidated by Aristotle (384-322 B.C.), in order to love others one has to learn to love one's self first. Esther loved her husband, but had eventually become worn-out of that love, so instead of being helpless to see the death of her love, she went into places where people were living on the edge every day, such as in the warring zones. She also applied to her life the Tangri tradition of forgetting one's personal history to keep the energy of love in constant movement; and ultimately went into Kazakhstan steppes in order to re-learn to love herself and God so that she can continue manifesting that love again. Self-love is also illustrated in the narrator's condition, and can be specifically cited in one of his conversations

with Marie, wherein he was trying to explain to her his desire of finding Esther:

"If I was to see her again, my face needed to be as clean as hers. Before I could find her, I must first find myself."

Redeeming love is also prevalent in the novels *Brida*, *By the River Piedra I Sat Down and Wept*, *Eleven Minutes*, and *The Zahir*. With the arrival of *Brida* in the Magus' life, his love for her emancipated him from his exile from the world and the things of the world. With Pilar's love for her boyfriend, he was able to rediscover his dream and mission. That love also saved him from possible life-long emotional catastrophe of broken dreams. With their love for each other, Maria was saved from the addiction of giving carnal pleasure, and Ralf came to know the real meaning of total love and the real purpose of sex. With Esther's love for her husband, he made a long pilgrimage to find and realize his dream, and with the same love, he started out on spiritual journey in order to re-discover himself that was lost along the way. The love of God is depicted in *By the River Piedra I Sat Down and Wept*, where second chances are given to those who ask for things from their hearts.

Obsessive love is one of the themes of *The Zahir*. The narrator's obsession to his wife started when she had disappeared for no apparent reason that she filled his thoughts, became the content of his every conversation, and continued to grow in his soul, until he started looking for her in every woman he would meet. Though he had continued to move on with his life, having a new girlfriend at that, he still was mystified and ever more absorbed by his wife's absence. The turbulence she had caused him was as strong as the attraction she had effected upon him. This inner turmoil drove him to search for her, and unintentionally for himself and for real love.

Fate and Will. The Oxford English Dictionary defines fate as-"the development of events outside a person's control regarded as decided in advance by a supernatural power"; whereas will is outlined as-"a person's power to decide on something and take action, or a person's ability to control his actions or thoughts". One of the key themes in the

selected novels of Paulo Coelho is the interlinked pair of fate and will theme, specifically how life is handled by destiny, and how it is controlled by willpower. Also, it portrays how one acts or responds to the situations presented by fate.

In Santiago's earlier conversation with Melchizedek, the old king told him that the world's greatest lie is that

"at certain point in our lives we lose control of what's happening to us, and our lives become controlled by fate."

He adhered to what fate has laid on before him before setting off his journey. On the other hand, when he lost his money to a swindler at the Port of Tangier, instead of letting fate decide for him, which obviously was to return to Andalusia, he instead opted to think of himself as an "adventurer in quest of his treasure". From then on, he always makes it a point that whatever fate throws in his way, he would make his own decisions with the help of the omens that guide his way.

Brida expounds the theme of fate and will by underlying the notion that one can be a master of his destiny, despite of the fact that one can easily commit mistakes, or flee from everything that he desires though that desire is quite near for him to realize. In addition, being a master of one's destiny also means to possess the capability of surrendering himself to Divine Providence or fate, and let God lead him to fight for his dreams, with the belief that these dreams are always realized at the perfectly right moment. To illustrate, Brida could have let go of her dream of becoming a witch after the Magus had left her alone to spend the night in the forest as her first lesson. However, she bounced back. She tried learning on her own through reading books, and with the help of the bookshop owner, she came to meet Wicca, who then became her teacher. She again attempted to quit the path to sorcery when she could not perform the very first assignment her teacher had asked her to do.

With Wicca's help, she became a full-fledged witch though she kept on committing mistakes, and even complaining along the way. One poignant and hard-learned lesson that Maria had

acquired was that sometimes life offers no second chances. Because of that, when fate presented her an opportunity to work in a foreign country, she grabbed it. When she found out that the dancing job was partly a ruse, instead of feeling sorry for herself, she chose to be an adventurer in search of treasure. From that moment on, she acted on whatever fate has presented her way.

Fate and will are portrayed in *By the River of Piedra I Sat Down and Wept* through taking risks in everyday occurrence. After so many years of not seeing Pilar's childhood friend, an opportunity to meet him has finally arrived through a conference in Madrid where he was the speaker. Despite her initial reservations, she gradually developed the attitude of taking risks and recognized the magic moment of each day.

In *The Zahir*, with Esther's disappearance, the narrator lived his life as normal as he could. However, because of his love for his wife, no matter how much he denied the truth from himself, he still wanted to find where she was. He responded to the guidance of fate in finding her with Mikhail being an instrument, and followed the signs along the way to know if he was trudging on the right path, and has performing the necessary things at the right time.

Vision of Life. Existentialism expresses that the human existence is an investigation of the meaning of being. This notion is further elaborated by Dreyfus who says that "The existence is inclusive of diverse possibilities from which man must make a selection, wherein he should remain committed to that selection, and each individual is adept in developing the very meaning of his own life based on what he personally regard as meaningful instead of what is rational (Muraleedharan, 2013)."

The Alchemist puts forth that whenever a person desires something with all his heart, all the Universe conspires to help him realize his dream. Therefore, it is important to know what one wants, and to follow this dream no matter what happens to the end because it is only by realizing one's self that one can justify his existence, and in turn, by that act, one can commune with the world; thus, affects change to the world, which is stated by Melchizedek; *"To realize one's destiny is the person's only real obligation. All things are one."*

Brida suggests that the ultimate mission of each individual is to find his or her soul mate. Apart from that, it also indicates that life is always a path of mystery, wherein to learn is to accept life's complexities, to make mistakes, to take risks and yet to believe that each moment is an act of faith. Thus, it suggests that the only way one could truly participate is by following his own desires, his own dreams, because that is how one becomes an instrument of God.

By the River Piedra I Sat Down and Wept, on the other hand, illustrates the unique attribute of each day. To live life to the fullest, it is essential that one "lives in the present...*day and learns to distinguish the magic moment-a moment in which we have the ability to change everything that makes us unhappy* because sometimes one small decision may have a huge role in changing the course of one's life."

Furthermore, Eleven Minutes elucidates the significance of taking risks, for sometimes life does not offer second chances

"...that what is lost once may be gone forever. In addition, it is also of great consequence to say yes to life by living it as if today were the first (or last) day of one's life."

Finally, The Zahir describes life's contradictions, yet to joyfully live life with whatever blessing one is given, despite its irony. As the narrator describes it,

"God knows that we are all artists of life. One day, he gives us a hammer with which to make sculptures, another day he gives us brushes and paints with which to make a picture, or a paper and a pencil to write with. But you cannot make a painting with a hammer, or a sculpture with a paintbrush. Therefore, however difficult it may be, I must accept today's small blessings, even if they seem like curses..."
"This is the only way I will manage to leave my pain behind and rebuild my life."

Religion and Spirituality. Religion and spirituality both refer to man's desire to find God or inner peace. While religion operates in literature and rituals for its worship, spirituality on the other hand, uses personalized prayer and meditation.

The Alchemist illustrates esotericism, a belief intended for or understood by only a small number of people with a specialized knowledge. Antoine Faivre identifies four essential characteristics of esotericism that includes: (a) connection between the invisible and visible parts of the universe; (b) the belief that nature is a living entity owing to a divine presence or life-force; (c) the need for mediating elements like symbols, rituals, angels, and visions to connect with spiritual knowledge; and (d) an experience of personal and spiritual transformation when arriving at this knowledge (Faivre, 2013). Apart from that, it also exemplifies a secret transference of spiritual teachings through initiation from master to disciple. Santiago became the alchemist's disciple inadvertently when the caravan joined by him reached the oasis, where the alchemist learned from the wind that someone in that caravan would be in need of his help. Conversely, Santiago prior to his meeting with the alchemist learned on his own about the world through reading the omens along the way, and by understanding the desert. So when the alchemist took in Santiago as his student, he enhanced his ability not only understand omens, but also listen to his heart, and most importantly in applying this spiritual knowledge to manifest in the physical plane by turning himself into the wind. In the act of doing so, Santiago discovered that God dwells in him; therefore he can accomplish great things.

On the other hand, Brida conveys a mixture of Wicca and Christian mysticism focusing on the Catholic tradition. Wicca is a combination of modern pagan and witchcraft religions. As an aspiring witch, Brida learned not only of the rituals and practices performed by the witches, but also of the existence, importance, and connection of the spirit world to the physical realm. On the other hand, Christian mysticism is practiced through ecstatic vision of the soul's mystical union with God and prayerful contemplation of the Holy Scripture. The novel reflects the fusion of the Wiccan mysticism and that of Christian

religion through the kingdom of the Moon's commemorative ritual to pray and pay homage to their forebears to be performed by Wicca and her students. They acknowledged not only the spirits of the ancients present in the ritual they had performed, but also of the protection of the Virgin Mary and Jesus Christ. Other than that, passages in the Bible became the point of reference in interpreting and explaining certain teachings, for example, Wicca referred to the Bible as containing all the true occult wisdom; thus, in order for Brida to find her gift, she must contemplate on the First Epistle of Saint Paul to the Corinthians which outlined the nine spiritual gifts.

Consequently, the Magus expressed that the teaching of the Tradition of the Sun, a way of teaching witchcraft, was described by Saint Paul in one of his epistles,

"And I was with you in weakness and in much fear and trembling; and my speech and my message were not in plausible words of wisdom, but in demonstration of the Spirit and of power, that your faith might not rest in the wisdom of men but in the power of God."

Apart from Bible references, mention of the teachings of the saints were also utilized, particularly the teachings of the Spanish mystic St. John of the Cross about faith in the form of the Dark of Night, and the martyrdom of St. Joan of Arc who was accused of witchcraft; thus, she was burned in fire as a sanction. Similarly, By the River of Piedra I Sat Down and Wept denotes Christian Mysticism in the context of Catholic tradition, however, in its more profound side.

In addition to the earlier description of Christian mysticism, the scholar McGinn (2005) described it as that part or element of Christian belief and practice that concerns the preparation for, the consciousness of, and the effect of a direct and transformative presence of God. One of its characteristics involves a community consisted of the Church and the believers. Therefore, involvement in a joint worship, such as the celebration of the Eucharist is indispensable in Christian mysticism. The practice of it involves

among others, visions or the sensory experiences; ecstasies; physical transformations, such as the development of stigmata or odor of sanctity; and the performance of miracles. The novel displays a person's search for God, particularly Pilar's friend. He travelled across many countries, including India and Egypt in order to find God, and it was only in the monastery in the Pyrenees that he finally met God and came to understand that every religion is right in its claim that God is the same even though He has a thousand names. He developed the ability of speaking and understanding in different tongues and performed the miracle of healing the sick through the help of the Virgin Mary.

Relatively, it also speaks about the feminine face of God-the Virgin Mary as having her own divinity. Pilar's friend explained it as: "The Bible tells that Jesus had two brothers. Virginity as it relates to Jesus, is based on a different thing: Mary initiated a new generation of grace. She is the cosmic bride, Earth, which opens to the heavens and allows itself to be fertilized. Because of the courage she showed in accepting her destiny, She allowed God to come down on earth-and she was transformed into the Great Mother

"...But you should know that this woman-the Goddess, the Virgin Mary, the Shechinah, the Great Mother, Isis, Sofia-is present in every religion on the face of the earth... In every religion and in every tradition, She manifests Herself in one form or another-She always manifests Herself. Since I am a Catholic, I perceive Her as the Virgin Mary."

The feminine face of God is also illustrated in The Zahir, where Mikhail was constantly guided by the apparition of the Virgin Mary.

Sex. It is one of the main themes of the novel Eleven Minutes. Nevertheless, the novel suggests two types of sex: (a) the profane and (b) the sacred. Sex is considered to be a sacrilege when sexual pleasure is performed for its own sake, and in that performance it is incorporated with pain and humiliation, like that of masochism, and sadism; and also, if it involves money in exchange of the pleasure it gives. Conversely, it is sacred if

the act of sex is performed in the context of love.

Prostitution. Apart from sex, *Eleven Minutes* also embraces the predominant theme of prostitution—the reasons for committing prostitution; how this undesirable profession can become an ally to those who seek for help—not only for those with sensual problems, but also for those who seek to unburden themselves with their day to day concerns; and the role despair plays in choosing the path of prostitution to change one's life.

Marriage. The *Zahir* displays apparently the theme of marriage. It expounds on the typical experience married couples undergo, how each manages his or her individual expectations, growth, and how to keep love alive and make the marriage last.

Narrative Techniques. Paulo Coelho uses his personal narrative techniques in the enhancement of the themes of his selected works, such as moral parable, ritual, religious miracle, fable, awkward question, and time frame.

Moral Parable. A moral parable is a story that is meant to illustrate, teach, and communicate important moral lesson in order to simplify complicated life situations; and thus, it conveys wisdom, beliefs, and lessons.

Together with the fable of the modified version of the story of Narcissus in the prologue, the moral parable concerning dreams, particularly that of the Roman centurion's most-quoted utterance in the Bible:

"My Lord, I am not worthy that you should come under my roof, but only speak a word and my servant will be healed."

Evidently, this adage strengthens the self-realization journey as well as the vision of life theme of *The Alchemist*. It symbolizes the significance of the conclusion of Santiago's journey: his real obligation lies in his self-realization, and whether he succeeds or fails, the world would be affected somehow, because all things are interconnected. In addition to that, it also foretells the contribution of the unfortunate episode that Santiago will be encountering in the Pyramids at the hands of the thieves in the ultimate search of his treasure at the

end of the novel.

The parable concerning the secret to happiness, where one ought not to forget to take pleasure in everyday life while performing his duties to realize his mission, as narrated by Melchizedek to Santiago not only serves as a guideline for him to follow, but foreshadows Santiago's journey, as well.

On the other, the parable about the builder and the planter found in the Prologue of the novel *Brida* suggests tacitly about the path of witchcraft, the direction in which *Brida* will be trudging on.

The story of the Other' introduces to the reader the subsequent total behavior change of Pilar in *By the River Piedra I Sat Down and Wept*. Accompanied with the recognition and seizure of magic moments and the notion of taking risks, the exercise of the Other' helped in Pilar's spiritual transformation journey towards self-realization. Apart from that, the story of the Other' also supplements and strengthens the themes Vision of Life, and Fate and Will, since together with Pilar's realization of the unique attributes of every moment, she decided then to concede to her true desires, thus, modifying her attitude towards every chance presented by fate, which eventually paved way to her completing the transformational journey.

The story in *Eleven Minutes* about the ripple in the lake as an aftermath of the tossing of a pebble where the duck nearby continued to swim provides the prelude to Maria's real journey towards the admittance of love in her life, thus, foreshadowing the bigger picture of Maria and Ralf's love story.

The Zahir utilizes quite many moral parables compared to the other selected novels. For one, the story about Hans' Question in a bar in Tokyo many centuries after Hitler succeeded in wiping out the "inferior race" in Asia in which he asked Fritz if the world is always what they knew it to be presented the nucleus of Esther's eventual disappearance in search for love and happiness. Like Hans, she also felt the same dissatisfaction, and she believed that the world is not at all the same regardless of what she knew about it; thus, unhappiness started to creep in. Meanwhile, the parable concerning the Cathedral, where the narrator considered it to be a reflection of his self,

emphasizes Esther's significance to his life. On the other hand, the story about the Master and the Buffalo signified dream-realization albeit the pain the dreamer experiences. It serves as a backdrop of the narrator's journey towards self-realization. In that, it compels the narrator to follow what his heart is telling him even though it might cost him pain. Alternatively, the parable about the circle of love talks about a protagonist, a monk whose name is Brother Porter who one day received a bunch of grapes from the farmer he had helped. Thinking of the Abbot who inspired him with the former's wisdom, he gave the grapes to the Abbot, and the Abbot passed it to the ailing monk, the monk gave it to the Cook, the Cook handed it to the Sacristan, and the Sacristan gave it to Brother Porter; thus, consequently completing the chain of love. The parable; thus, tells also of the constant movement of love, and how it could be obstructed by one selfish act.

This parable foreshadows the reason of Esther's dwelling in the Kazakhstan steppes and Mikhail's narration of Esther's story in front of the beggars and the narrator in order to continue the flow of the energy of love. Then, the parable about the two firemen who extinguished forest fire, serves as the backstory that adds meaning to the theme of self-love, where Esther has to learn to love herself again so that she can continue loving her husband, likewise, the narrator has to find himself first so that he can find Esther. Ultimately, the parable of the railway tracks whose never-changing distance of 143.5 centimeters apart is akin to the defamiliarization device that construes the theme of marriage. The narrator's realization of the permanent distance of the railway tracks imposed by the Romans a long time ago is similar to the laws and customs followed by many married couples. Even if both have outgrown the other, for one party wants to find himself or herself in order to serve their family well, the restrictions put forth by society and some other marital considerations such as the plight of the children hold both parties together but they remain stagnant and unable to grow. Nevertheless, this is not applied to the narrator's marriage with Esther for she left him in pursuit of her happiness.

Ritual. It is defined as a type of routine behavior that symbolizes or expresses something.

As a symbolic activity, it is no longer confined to religion, but is distinguished from technical action (Talal, 1993). Furthermore, rituals are to be performed in a disciplined manner whose appropriate performance is contained not only within the interpretation of the symbols, but extends to the acquisition of the abilities consistent with the rules allowed by those in authority (Talal, 1993).

The ritual of the payment of ten percent of Santiago's flock as tithe required by Melchizedek suggests the other profound theme of the novel, which is, religion and spirituality. Apart from that, it also foretells that Santiago's journey is a solemn one. In addition, the prayer ritual prescribed by the leader of the caravan before starting on their desert sojourn portends the gravity of the decision Santiago made pertaining to his search for his dreams, including the tests and the challenges he would be facing.

The hospitality showed by the oasis tribal chiefs to the newly-arrived caravan group serves as the background to the forthcoming turning point in Santiago's life: the intensification of his ability to understand the language of the world through reading the flights of hawks. As a consequence, he has been offered the job of oasis counselor, the finding of the love of his life, the meeting of the alchemist, and the crucial decision to leave every beautiful thing behind and press on with his search. Finally, the ritual of waiting by Fatima after Santiago left the oasis through sending of kisses to the desert wind confirms to the reader of the positive outcome of Santiago's journey; and thus, it also insinuates that somewhere in the future they will be together again.

Correspondingly, the use of the rite of passage, a kind of ritual, is also applied in *The Alchemist* signposting the journey of Santiago to self-realization. It is manifested largely on the episodes where the alchemist emerged in the life of Santiago. The rite of passage is a ritual that symbolizes a person's conversion from one status to another; consequently, involves three phases, namely: separation, transition, and incorporation (Bell, 2013). In the separation stage, the initiates are detached from their previous identities through physical and symbolic measures. Conversely, the transition period depicts ritual

ordeals or ritual training where the initiates are in ambiguous position as their old identities were removed without yet acquiring a new one. Finally, the incorporation characteristically confirms the new identities and community of the initiates (Turner, 1969).

Santiago's old self—that of being a simple shepherd was initially removed from him when he said yes to Melchizedek. From that point, he started understanding his path through reading the omens. He embarked on a journey in quest of his personal legend crossing the Strait of Gibraltar and reached the Port of Tangier where he lost all his money to a swindler, and he chose to continue his sojourn with the spirit of an adventurer. As he embraced that attitude, he further harnessed the skill of understanding omens, ventured into learning to understand the language of the world, and recognized the life-changing moments like the notion of the beginner's luck and the principle of favorability. His transformation still continues with the alchemist taking him as his student after the former tested not only his courage but also the accuracy of his vision, as well as his ability to find the characteristics necessary for self-realization. Apart from these tests, the alchemist taught him about learning through action, that is, the manifestation of the spiritual world to the physical realm; of listening to one's heart; of being aware of the interconnection of both the animate and inanimate things, and understanding the constant transformation of every matter, so that each could serve his/her own designated purpose that would eventually result to the individual's communion with God and with the world. By employing all the necessary lessons Santiago learned along the way, and through the act of turning himself into the wind, he was finally incorporated as a self-realized individual.

Conversely, in *Brida*, the title character has to go through the sequences of the rite of passage' in order to become a witch. With her latent abilities, Wicca instructed her to perform on a daily basis the ritual of spreading and understanding the tarot at the same hour for two weeks. This stage encouraged Brida to separate from her normal persona and slowly wake her mystic side. Once Wicca had successfully determined Brida's gift through the performance of the gift awakening

ritual, Brida was then placed in rigorous training involving the different mysteries of witchcraft. It woke up the dormant voice of her soul that signified her readiness for the Initiation so that she could be accepted to the community of the witches. However, before she could be initiated, she needed to transform all her knowledge by crossing the invisible bridge of magic through the force of sex. After passing the requirements, she was finally incorporated as a full-fledged witch through the witches' Initiation.

Apart from the rite of passage', as a student of witchcraft, she has learned to use the ritual of words, where she should be careful in the words she speaks for apart from everything, God manifests His will through words. Therefore, it prescribes to the reader that Wicca religion is not only characterized with reverence for all things, but also is highly particular in spirituality, and is even superstitious.

In *By the River Piedra I Sat Down and Wept*, Pilar and her boyfriend were engaged in church visitation whenever they would reach a particular town or village. The ritual of a church visit reinforces the context of spirituality of the novel, as well as the feminine face of God. It suggests to the readers that the notion of the Great Mother is long-time inculcated in the Catholic tradition, and it reintroduces Catholicism in another approach.

Furthermore, it also serves as a catalyst in Pilar's spiritual transformational journey. In each church that she visits, she grasps not only of an understanding of her own self, but also the rediscovery of her faith, and her reconnection with one of the fundamental beliefs of her childhood religion: the divinity of the Great Mother: the Virgin Mary. Apart from that, it also serves as a device where the feminine face of God is explained. Additionally, it provides a backdrop for the formation of the central event in the novel, which introduces the feast of the Immaculate Conception as the core of the religion and spirituality theme. Finally, the church visit ritual also symbolizes the development of Pilar and her friend's love story. It was in the monastery of Piedra that they realized that they loved each other, that they rekindled their lost love, straightened up their past issues, and realized the veracity of their feelings. In conclusion, it is in the monastery of Piedra that

they re-claimed their victory of love.

Contrariwise, Pilar silently urged her boyfriend to break the glasses as “a rite of passage”, which signifies that they had to liberate themselves from whatever that traps them emotionally and spiritually, before they can partake in the mystery of love. Lastly, the ritual of writing her love story and tossing it into the riverbed of the River Piedra connotes the end of Pilar and her boyfriend’s suffering, and foretells of a new life together, of living out their mission.

In *Eleven Minutes*, the rituals that include gift-giving, invoking of desire, and exploring each other’s body through physical touch enacted by Maria and Ralf in order to re-acquaint each other to their respective self, enhances the meaning of their journey towards love, and ultimately, in finding their individual selves again.

Maria’s ritual of diary writing gives a glimpse to her soul, her feelings, her mind, and her point of view. It aids the readers in the profound understanding of what is happening as the story progresses. Furthermore, it also facilitates in exposing the connection of obscure links of the narration. As a final point, the diary writing also serves as the indicator of Maria’s progress in her search for love, in living and understanding her life.

In *The Zahir*, one of the rituals featured is the dance ritual performed in the Armenian restaurant in order to evoke the energy of love in homage to the Virgin Mary. The dance ritual reflects the actual spiritual and love journey that Esther is embarking. It also foreshadows the narrator’s own spiritual journey. The ritual of giving blood-stained cloth in commemoration of the soldier who died in the battlefield, but whose death was a significant one, symbolizes of the prize the narrator would get upon completion of his self-realization journey.

Ultimately, the ritual performed by Dos in the Kazakh steppes in accordance to the Tengri tradition serves as the culminating point of the narrator’s self-realization journey, where he was able to learn what he needs to learn about love, about his self, and about the true meaning of life. Also, the ritual connotes that the narrator deserves to reclaim his wife and to be given the bloodstained cloth-the sign of having known the

true meaning of love and life.

Religious Miracle. Baker’s Dictionary of the Bible defines a religious miracle as “an event in the external world brought about by the immediate agency or the simple volition of God.” It occurs to show that the power behind it is not limited to the laws of matter or mind as it interrupts fixed natural laws.

Santiago’s capacity to turn himself into the wind signifies the interconnection of all the elements-that every act an individual performs does not only require collective assistance from others and help from the hand that wrote all, but also of the faith of the performer. With these, Santiago was able to perform a miracle.

The celebration of the feast of the Immaculate Conception is the setting where *By the River Piedra I Sat Down and Wept* religious miracle happened. With the aid of the rituals performed including prayer, chanting, and invocation of the Holy Spirit and of the Virgin Mary, Pilar was able to receive the gifts of tongue and of discernment from the Holy Spirit. The miracle in the celebration per se further introduced the capacity of the Great Mother to love, and through Pilar’s understanding of love, the theme of love in the novel becomes well-defined.

The Zahir makes use of the apparition of the Virgin Mary to Mikhail. With such vision, She guides him towards the fulfillment of his mission-that is, to spread love with Esther’s help. The role of the Virgin Mary in the novel strengthens the theme of recognition of the feminine face of God, the Virgin Mary being the primary deity in the novel.

Fable. A fable is usually a short narrative making an edifying or cautionary point and often employing as characters, the animals that speak and act like humans. It is also a story about mythical or supernatural beings or events.

The modified version of the story about Narcissus found in the prologue of *The Alchemist* serves as the backdrop of one of the central themes of the novel: vision of life and the interconnection of all the things. It manifests that by realizing one’s purpose in life, one also contributes value to the world.

In *Eleven Minutes*, Paulo Coelho incorporated Plato’s story of man and woman’s separation from

one body. According to the story, a long time ago, a man and a woman were joined together in a single body, with one head but two faces, two sets of arms and of legs, and two sets of sex organs. Because of the creature's potential power, the Greek gods became jealous that Zeus separated them with his lightning bolt. Because of this division, man and woman have to find their other halves. The story presented is an added substance to the other facet of sex: its spiritual side. Aside from that, it sets the milieu of Maria's confusion about her current profession; thus, she continued her journey to find love despite her distasteful occupation.

Awkward Question. An awkward question is a question marked by or causing embarrassment or discomfort.

The Magus asked Brida if she would give up everything she had learned and would learn about magic and mysteries if she found the love of her life. This question brought discomfort to Brida since for her, love is important, but judging on the Magus' way of life, there is a possibility that he could not understand romantic love. However, the awkward question serves as "a rite of passage" for the Magus to accept her as his student. Apart from that, it also serves as a backdrop of one of the themes of the novel, which is the vision of life, wherein the ultimate destiny of man on earth is to find his soul mate.

In *Eleven Minutes*, the awkward reality of the actual amount of time spent on the act of sex, which is eleven minutes, forms the basis of the title of the novel. It also signifies the fact discovered by Maria upon carrying out her job as a commercial sex worker.

Love and Marriage are some of the themes presented in *The Zahir*. Awkward questions pertaining to male erection, inter-office affair, and a man's wife being the object of desire of another man are some of the questions which society represses to ask due to the discomfort they cause. However, in the novel, these questions elucidate some of the marital concerns, which married couples pretend not wanting to know about and pretend not to ask. On the other hand, these questions form part of the so-called instances of the "lack of love", where in its disguise, love is killed. As a result, these awkward questions shape the narrator's journey in finding his wife again for

he must know the instances where love is killed without one's intention of doing it.

Time Frame. Collins English Dictionary defines time frame as "the period of time within which certain events are scheduled to occur."

The *Alchemist* employs the time frame of today or the present in order to emphasize that it is in the present that one should focus on and take advantage of, and by doing what is required on that day. Conversely, a period of three days was given to Santiago to turn himself into the wind, indicating the resurrection of Jesus, which figuratively denotes the spiritual rebirth of Santiago through the realization that God's spirit dwells in him, thus, he can perform miracles. Similarly, Brida emphasizes the time frame of today, adding a more mystical touch to the spirituality of the novel.

The emphasis of today in *By the River Piedra I Sat Down and Wept* fortifies the principle of seizing the magic moment adopted by Pilar on herself towards self-realization as each day is different from every other day. In addition to that, the novel's plot makes use of the seven-day time frame, describing the love story of Pilar and her boyfriend. With the integration of the present in the seven-day time frame, the reader is insinuated of the importance of time in the development of an event.

V. CONCLUSION

Paulo Coelho's selected novels illustrate the common themes in man's life, such as his or her quest for self-realization, as well as his or her search for happiness in the form of love. The study finds out that these novels portray not only the literal journey of characters but also reflect the journey towards self-actualization through spiritual enlightenment and dream-realization. Thus, the study concludes that a man can fulfill his or her destiny when he or she has contributed something to the world that can affect change.

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